

VillageMath Educational Review

An International/Multidisciplinary Journal of
Network for Grassroots Science and Mathematics
Education (The VillageMath Network)

A publication of VillageMath Educational Services
(CAC RC: 4097888)

Volume 7, Issue 1

January, 2025

CODEN: VERIAU

Assessing Item Parameter Drift of 2019-2022 National Examination Council Mathematics Essay Questions in Benue State, Nigeria

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14760021>

Article History: Received 4th September, 2024; Revised 4th January, 2025; Published 29th January, 2025.

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How to Cite this Article:

Upu, C. N., Obinne, A. D. E., Aduloju, M. O., & Agi, C. I. (2024). Assessing Item Parameter Drift of 2019-2022 National Examination Council Mathematics Essay Questions in Benue State, Nigeria. *VillageMath Educational Review (VER)*, 7(1), 1-18.

<https://ngsme.villagemath.net/journals/ver/v7i1/upu-obinne-aduloju-agi>

Abstract

The study on Assessing Item Parameter Drift of 2019-2022 National Examination Council Mathematics Essay Questions in Benue State, Nigeria, was meant to check the item parameters to ascertain if drift exist. The population of the study was 18754 senior secondary three (SS3) students from the 258 senior secondary schools in Benue State who registered for 2023 NECO Mathematics paper II examination. The sample size for this study was 408 students from intact classes of SS3 students from the different schools. The sampling for this study was in multi-stages. A counter-balanced research design was used. Four instruments were used for data collection. The instruments were past examination essay Mathematics Questions of NECO 2019-2022 which were adopted. Item parameters of difficulty and discrimination were calibrated using GPCM built in X-calibre. One way ANOVA was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level. The study revealed that there

was no significant drift in both the mean difficulty and discrimination index of the items. There was a negative (low) drift in the mean difficulty index of NECO Mathematics essay test items of 2019-2022. The item discrimination of 2019-2022 exhibited both medium and a negative (low) drift. Based on the results of the findings, the study concludes that the item parameters of NECO Mathematics essay test items with negative difficulty and discrimination parameters need to be reviewed to ensure that when used in future examinations the test quality would be improved.

Keywords: Assessment, Item Parameter Drift, Mathematics Examination, NECO, Mathematics Essay Questions, Measurement and Evaluation

Introduction

Nigeria's philosophy of education is based on the beliefs that education is an instrument for excellence, national development and social change. This philosophy of Nigeria's education laid emphasis on the development of individuals to be sound and effective citizens and the provision of equal opportunities for all citizens of the nation at all levels both inside and outside the formal school system. This means that education is geared to provide standards to good citizenry in search for solutions to problems such as corruption, gender discrimination and emerging issues including global warming, religious radicalization and terrorism (Agu & Samuel, 2018).

In Nigeria, for one to gain admission into a higher education, one must possess a credit pass in Mathematics. Mathematics is defined as a brilliant vehicle for the advancement and enhancement of an individuals' academic capability in logical thinking, spatial perception, analytical and abstract idea (Adegoke, 2013). Mathematics is well utilized in banking, medicine, aviation, climate change monitoring and demographic feasibility studies. Mathematics helps students to develop numeracy, reasoning, critical thinking and problem solving skills through learning and application to enhance national development.

The development of every nation depends mainly on the scientific and technological breakthrough of the country which is built upon Mathematics. This is because every individual needs some measure of Mathematics for his or her day to day activities. Mathematics play a key role towards the actualization of the scientific and technological advancement in the society and enables individuals to live efficiently within the global world. The usefulness of Mathematics in human activities cannot be underestimated because it is the precursor of scientific discoveries and inventions, of which any nation that overlooks the study of Mathematics and does not take interest in it would remain underdeveloped. The Federal Government of Nigeria has for long been aware of the pivotal position of Mathematics to individual fulfilment and national development goals with particular reference to scientific and technological emancipation and breakthrough. This understanding has consequently led educational policy makers to position Mathematics as an essential consideration for successful achievement in certificate examination bodies like the Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSCE) conducted by West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO) as well as placement examinations like Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination (UTME) conducted by Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB). This is why Nigerian

government places great emphasis on the teaching and learning of all the subjects including Mathematics by making it a core and compulsory subject from basic to secondary levels of education.

As important as Mathematics is, there has been a downward trend in students' achievement in the subject. The percentage of students who pass the subject at credit level showed that from 2019 to 2022, the percentages of students with credit pass and above was 47%, 45%, 44.5% and 48.3% which is less than 50% (Ministry of Education, 2021; NECO Chief Examiner reports, 2019-2022). This poor achievement could be as a result of the nature of items used in the successive years. Students' poor achievement in Mathematics over the years have been attributed to the fact that the subject is difficult and that the teaching methodology has not been appropriate as well as the students' attitudes towards Mathematics and gender differences of the students (Ogbu, Musa, Kurumed & Tyoor, 2018). In a related development, researchers such as Matawal (2013) and Osu (2018) have identified various factors that affect students' achievement in Mathematics especially at the secondary school level. Prominent among these factors are the nature of the test items for the assessment and the learners' characteristics.

The achievement of an examinee on test items can be explained by the ability of the examinee and characteristics of the items. Test items are set of questions which are designed to measure the knowledge, intelligence, ability, traits, skills, aptitude, interest, attitude which an individual exhibits (Opara, 2014). These questions follow a systematic procedure for observing an individual's behaviour as well as describing such behaviour or achievement by numerical scale or category. Test items are composed of series of questions designed to measure the different types of behaviours in all fields of education. Test items achieve its aim when the test items meet psychometrical properties/quality of item parameters. The quality of test items are of much importance since results from the items are summed and used in students certification by assessment organizations

Assessment in education is the classification of persons with respect to their worth. Assessment outcomes provide valuable information that may be used to improve educational activities and as such the appropriate development and use of these assessments are essential requirements for responsible professional practices in educational testing and measurement. Educational policy makers, administrators and educators use results of the assessment obtained from achievement test instrument to evaluate how students are doing from year to year. However, achievement test administered each year; differ from each other to ensure test security. Practically, no test developer can guarantee the equivalency of different test forms despite vigorous efforts to ensure that equivalency. This is because large scale examination bodies like National Examination Council rely mostly on bank of achievement test items to select from when building their cognitive assessments. The quality of assessments depends on the quality of items in their item banks which makes maintenance of item banks overtime to be critical to ensure that test items meet the psychometric properties that are expected of them. This will be feasible through a check on the item parameters.

Item parameters are statistical indicators that define the quality of an item in the instrument employed (Orheruata, 2015). These statistical indicators are item difficulty,

discrimination, guessing and carelessness parameters. Item difficulty parameter refers to the examinee's ability level at which approximately half of the examinees are likely to answer a particular item correctly. Item discrimination parameter describes the strength of an item discriminating between examinee with trait level (θ) below and above the threshold while guessing parameter is the probability of getting the item correct by guessing alone (Chen, 2013; Orheruata, 2015), the four-parameter model considers the probability that high ability respondents select the wrong option due to carelessness or fatigue (William & David, 2021). A well-developed test needs to have its item parameters in conformity with the theoretical framework for item selection and calibration using appropriate test theories such as IRT. According to Item Response Theory framework, examinees ability estimation ranges from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$ in theory, while in practice, the values usually are between -3 to +3 which is the acceptable theoretical scale for item parameter. The probability of getting an item correct is a function of the examinee's ability and item parameters (Kim & Lee, 2017).

Item parameters may change overtime due to changes in curriculum, frequent exposure of items and other reasons. Over the years, test items selected and kept in item banks of examination bodies are reused. Each reuse increases the probability that an item is exposed or made available to examinees prior to testing day (Beyza, 2017). Exposed items can give later examinees specific, prior knowledge of the test content. When this happens, the test item may no longer measure the intended construct, but rather examinee's can use outside resources to determine a correct response or examinee's ability to remember the correct response when the item is presented in the test will be on what the examinee has practiced before the test item is presented. When this happens, items are considered to have changed from the item parameters and become easy or less discriminating than their true estimates (Krause, 2012).

When the same form of examination is in continuous usage for a period of time, items could have been exposed, allowing later examinees to have prior knowledge of specific items on the examination. This could be as a result of examinees constantly using past questions to revise in preparation for the examination with the idea of some questions being repeated. Changes in the interaction between test items and examinees often results in the changes in the item parameter values from the initial calibrated items from the item pool. This change in the item parameter values over time is referred to as item parameter drift (IPD) (Orheruata, Omorougiuwa & Osunde, 2017). The authors state that item parameter drift is the shift from psychometric properties of item parameter estimates. IPD occurs when invariance no longer holds, and there is a differential change in item parameters overtime. IPD can also occur when there is no enough time to answer the questions in a test. Not providing sufficient time results in individuals being unable to reach certain items at the end of the test and these items appear more difficult than they actually are. If this problem persists in successive tests administrations, errors pile up and lead to drift. IPD threatens the validity of scores (Yoon, 2011). The occurrence of IPD in a test administration negatively affects the validity of inferences from test scores. IPD affects the pass and fail decisions (Ibrahim & Sahin-Kursad, 2022). On successive test administrations, tests for IPD are conducted to verify whether item parameters are consistent overtime or not. Several studies

have been done on IPD in different areas of study using multiple options but very rare on essay items (Ayanwale, 2017).

Essay items are questions which requires a student to compose a response either one or more sentences, draw and labelled a diagram or by solving a mathematical problem. Essay items provides student with the opportunity to explain their understanding and demonstrate creativity but makes it hard for students to arrive at an acceptable answer by emptiness. The increased use of essay items can be attributed to its role in validity. The current trends in the achievement of students in Mathematics at SSCE administered by National Examinations Council shows examinees' consistent fluctuating and poor achievement over the years is attributed to validity and reliability of item parameter (Musa, Joshua & Titilayo, 2018). Validity of Mathematics essay test refers to the degree to which evidence and theory support the interpretation of scores obtained by the items of essay tests. Emaikwu (2019) describes validity as the extent to which results of evaluation procedure serve the particular uses for which they are intended. Essay items are very important in assessing student because skills and knowledge, such as complex competencies, direct performances, or explication of reasoning that cannot be fully measured when only multiple choice (MC) items are used for testing students' achievement particularly in Mathematics. Essay items also measure the abilities of low and high performing students more accurately and also avoid testwiseness that can occur when only MC items are administered (Han & Guo, 2011). Essay items carry more marks, this means that essay items are the determinants of passing or failing an examination.

Available literature review shows that there is limited research on IPD especially on essay Mathematics questions of NECO in Benue State. As a result of this, there is need to determine the psychometric properties of the examination items used to determine the performance of students. Examinee ability is obtained from the score an individual obtains from a test and this really depends on the quality of the test taken. Determination of the psychometric properties of examination items are important to ensure public examinations items possess good psychometric properties that are expected of the items used for examination purpose or the parameter does not change. Based on the above, the problem of this study is to assess item parameter drift of NECO Mathematics essay examination from 2019-2021 in Benue State, Nigeria.

Research Objectives

The main purpose of the study is to assess Item Parameter Drift of NECO Mathematics Essay Examination questions of 2019-2021 in Benue State, Nigeria.

Specifically, the study seeks to:

- i. Determine the difficulty index of NECO Mathematics Essay test items from 2019-2022.
- ii. Determine the discrimination index of NECO Mathematics Essay test items from 2019-2022.
- iii. Determine if there is drift in difficulty index of NECO Mathematics Essay test items of 2019-2022.
- iv. Check for drift in discrimination parameter of NECO Mathematics Essay test items from 2019-2022.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

- i. What is the difficulty index of NECO Mathematics Essay test items from 2019-2022?
- ii. What is the discrimination index of NECO Mathematics Essay test items from 2019-2022?
- iii. How do NECO Mathematics Essay test items drifted in the difficulty parameter from 2019-2022?
- iv. How do NECO Mathematics Essay test items drifted in the discrimination parameter from 2019-2022?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are formulated and will be tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- i. The drift in the mean difficulty index of NECO Mathematics Essay test items of 2019-2022 do not significantly differ.
- ii. The drift in the mean discrimination index of NECO Mathematics Essay test items of 2019-2022 do not significantly differ.

Methodology

This study made use of a counterbalance research design. This is a kind of design where by all subjects receive equal treatment at different intervals. In this study, all the subjects have been taught by their various teachers using the approved syllabus in preparation of NECO examination. Therefore, all the subjects responded to the three instruments at different intervals.

The population of the study comprised all 18754 senior secondary three students from the 258 senior secondary schools in Benue State who registered for 2023 NECO Mathematics paper II examination and are awaiting to write the exams (Benue State Ministry of Education, Students' registration record, 2023). The sample size for this study was the intact classes of SS3 students from the different schools which was 1632 students. The sampling for this study was in multi-stages. Purposive sampling technique was used to select 2 schools from each senatorial district (zone A, B and C).

Purposive sampling was used to select the period of study to include the examination years of 2019-2022. Simple random technique was used to select 2 local government areas from each senatorial district of the State to be used. Also, the six schools to be used for the study were selected through simple random technique. Four instruments were used for data collection. The instruments were past examination essay Mathematics Questions of NECO 2019-2022 titled: General Mathematics Paper II (GMPII) A, B, C and D according to the different years. Each of the instruments has two parts: I and II. Part I has five items with each question carrying 8 marks while Part II has seven items with each question carrying 12 marks. The candidates are to answer all the items in Part I and only five items in Part II. Part I has a total of 40 marks and Part II has a total of 60 marks. The instructions and time allowed was strictly as NECO has given on each of the paper. The instruments (GMP II) to be used for data collection are standardized instruments administered by NECO for the

period of 2019-2022. The instrument were adopted and used as they are without any changes. To ensure that changes are avoided, the items were scanned and printed.

The researchers carried out a simulation study to enable them get the data for this study. This was because GMP II is not marked electronically and not even marked in Benue State where it is written. The possibility of the researchers getting the item by item responses with the marks earned by each candidate was not feasible. The researchers however got the marking schemes of the successive years from NECO Board to enable the marking of GMP II examination that was administered by the researchers.

The researchers administered the instruments in third term when the teachers had finished preparing the students for NECO examinations. The instruments were administered at an interval of 4 days at different times with the help of the research assistants to check how consistently stable they are over the period under study. The research assistants collected the scripts on the same day at the end of the time allowed for the GMP II examination and hand it over to the researchers. Thereafter, the researcher handed the scripts to the research assistants who are NECO examiners to mark and score the scripts based on the marking scheme of NECO examination board approved for the successive years under study. After the scripts were marked by the research assistants, the researchers cross-checked the scripts to ensure that the scores were in line with the marking scheme.

The data was analysed using descriptive statistics of Mean and Percentages. The rule of thumb guided the answering of research questions while One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Below is the Thumbs rule for item parameter determination, based on IRT (Pedro, 2016; Issayeva, 2022).

Trait Level	Difficulty-Level
High	(1.5 and above)
Medium	(0- 1.49)
Low	(-1.5 and below)
Discrimination	Interpretation
0.40 and above	Very discriminating/very good items
0.30 – 0.39	Discriminating/good items
0.20 – 0.29	Moderately discriminating item.
0.10 – 0.19	Not discriminating/ Marginal item
Below 0.1	Poor / questionable items.

Results

This section presents the results and discussion of findings of the study.

Research Question One

What is the difficulty index of NECO Mathematics Essay test items from 2019-2022?

To answer research question one, the data was subjected to Generalized Partial Credit Analysis built in X-calibre and the result is presented in table 1a and 1b. While table 1a shows

the difficulty parameter of the items for each of the four years, table 1b shows the percentage summary of the difficulty parameter.

Table 1a: Analysis of Generalized Partial Credit Model of Difficulty ('B' Parameter Estimates) of 2019-2022 NECO Mathematics Essay Test

Difficulty parameter for each of the NECO Mathematics examination items of 2019-2022								
Items	2019	Remarks	2020	Remarks	2021	Remarks	2022	Remarks
1	1.60	High	-1.03	Low	0.45	Medium	0.44	Medium
2	0.48	Medium	1.56	High	1.88	High	1.93	High
3	0.42	Medium	1.52	High	0.42	Medium	1.55	High
4	1.82	High	0.44	Medium	1.50	High	0.65	Medium
5	0.39	Medium	0.45	Medium	1.49	Medium	-1.07	Low
6	1.61	High	-1.50	Low	-1.10	High	1.87	High
7	0.42	Medium	1.46	Medium	1.79	High	1.78	High
8	1.92	High	0.45	Medium	-1.02	Low	0.54	Medium
9	0.35	Medium	-1.01	Low	0.35	Medium	0.68	Medium
10	-1.92	Low	1.70	High	1.55	High	1.64	High
11	-1.45	Low	0.44	Medium	-1.03	Low	1.90	High
12	-1.73	Low	1.65	High	0.18	Medium	-1.56	Low
Mean	0.32		0.44		0.54		0.86	
SD	1.31		1.09		1.12		1.12	

Key: High (1.5 and above), Medium (0.0 – 1.49), Low (-1.0 and below)

Table 1a shows the item difficulty of the 12 items of NECO Mathematics Essay questions from 2019 to 2022. The items were classified based on the trait level of High, Medium and Low.

In 2019, four (4) items (Q1, Q4, Q6 and Q8) were classified as high, five items (5) (Q2, Q3, Q5, 7 and Q9) were medium and three (3) items (Q10, Q11 and Q12) were low.

In 2020, four (4) items (Q2, Q3, Q10 and Q12) were high, five (5) items (Q4, Q5, Q7, Q8 and Q11) were medium and three (3) items, (Q1, Q9 and Q6) were low.

In 2021, six (6) items, (Q2, Q4, Q5, Q6, Q7 and Q10) were high, four (4) items, (Q1, Q3, Q9 and Q12) were medium and two (2) items, (Q8 and Q11) were low.

In 2022, six (6) items, (Q2, Q3, Q6, Q7, Q10, and Q11) were high, four (4) items, (Q1, Q4, Q8 and Q9) were medium and two (2) items, (Q5 and Q12) were low.

Table 1b: Summary of item difficulty for NECO Mathematics Essay Questions of 2019-2022

Year	High	Medium	Low	Total
2019	4 items	5 items	3 items	12
Percentage	33%	42%	25%	100
2020	4 items	5 items	3 items	12
Percentage	33%	42%	25%	100
2021	5 items	5 items	2 items	12
Percentage	42%	42%	17%	100

2022	6 items	4 items	2 items	12
Percentage	50%	33%	17%	100

Table 1b shows the percentage distribution of item difficulty of NECO Mathematics easy examinations in 2019 to 2022. The results indicate that in 2019, 33% of the items were high, 42% of the items were medium and 25% of the items were low. Also in 2020, 33% of the items were high, 42% of the items were medium and 25% were low in difficulty index.

In 2021, 42% of the items were high, 42% of the items were medium and 17% of the items were low. Lastly, in 2022, 50% of the items were high, 33% of the items were medium while 17% of the items were low in difficulty index.

Research Question Two

What is the discrimination index of NECO Mathematics Essay test items from 2019-2022?

To answer research question two, the data was subjected to Generalized Partial Credit Analysis built in X-calibre and the result is presented in table 2a and 2b. While table 2a shows the discrimination parameter of the items for each of the four years, table 2b shows the percentage summary of the difficulty parameter.

Table2a: Analysis of Generalized Partial Credit Model of Discrimination Indices ('A' Parameter Estimates) of 2019 to 2022 NECO Mathematics Essay Test

Year	2019		2020		2021		2022	
Item	a ₁	Remarks	a ₂	Remarks	a ₃	Remarks	a ₄	Remarks
1	0.31	Good	0.26	Moderate	0.38	Good	0.45	Very Good
2	0.41	Very Good	0.43	Very good	0.36	Good	0.49	Very good
3	-0.18	Poor	-0.17	Poor	-0.22	Poor	0.55	Very good
4	0.48	Very Good	0.48	Very good	0.53	Very Good	-0.05	Poor
5	0.51	Very Good	0.37	Good	0.39	Very Good	0.54	Very Good
6	0.43	Very Good	0.36	Good items	0.43	Very Good	0.53	Very Good
7	0.50	Very Good	0.48	Very Good	0.52	Very Good	-0.09	Poor
8	0.40	Very Good	0.38	Good	0.36	Good	0.52	Very good
9	0.23	Moderate	0.26	Moderate	0.23	Moderate	0.43	Very Good
10	0.37	Good	0.39	Good	0.14	Marginal	0.41	Very Good
11	0.49	Very Good	0.41	Very Good	0.47	Very Good	0.54	Very Good
12	0.49	Very Good	0.19	Marginal	0.48	Very Good	0.44	Very Good
	Mean	Good	Mean	Good	Mean	Good	Mean	Good
	= 0.37		= 0.32		= 0.34		= 0.39	

a₁ = item discrimination Parameter indices of 2019, a₂ = item discrimination Parameter

indices of 2020, a_3 = item discrimination Parameter indices of 2021, and a_4 = item discrimination Parameter indices of 2021

Table 2a presents the item discrimination indices of the Mathematics Easy test items of NECO for the period of four years from 2019-2022. From the table, the criterion for classification of items is based on the guidelines stipulated by (Pedro, 2016, Orheruata, *et al*, 2017, Hambleton & Swaminathan, 2013). These items are classified as: Very discriminating/very good items, discriminating/good items, moderately discriminating, not discriminating/Marginal items and Poor. Items with discrimination indices greater than 0.40 are very discriminating/very good items, those with discrimination indices from 0.30 to 0.39 are discriminating/good items, those with item discrimination indices from 0.20 to 0.29 are moderately discriminating and those with item discrimination indices from 0.10 to 0.19 are not discriminating/marginal items and items below 0.10 are regarded as poor/questionable items.

In 2019, eight (8) items (Q2, Q4- Q8, Q11 and Q12) were very good discriminating and regarded as very good items with the indices of 0.40-0.51. Two items(2) items (Q1 and Q10) were discriminating and regarded as good items with the indices of 0.31- 0.37, one (1) item (Q9) was moderate with an index of 0.23 and one item (Q3) was poor with an index of -0.18.

In 2020, four (4) items (Q2, Q4, Q7 and Q11) were very discriminating and regarded as very good items with the indices of 0.41-0.48. Four (4) items (Q5, Q6, Q8 and Q10) were discriminating and regarded as good items with the indices of 0.36-0.39. Two items (Q1 and Q9) were moderate with an index of 0.26 each. One (1) item (Q12) was not discriminating and regarded as a marginal item with an index of 0.19 while (Q3) was poor with an index of -0.17.

In 2021, five (5) items, (Q4, Q6, Q7, Q11 and Q12) were very discriminating and regarded as very good items with the indices of 0.43-0.53. Four (4) items (Q1, Q2, Q5 and Q8) were discriminating and regarded as good items with the indices of 0.36-0.39. One item (Q9) was moderate with an index of 0.23. One (1) item Q10 was not discriminating and regarded as a marginal item with an index of 0.14 while one(1) item (Q3) was poor with an index of -0.22.

In 2022, ten (10) items (Q1-Q3,Q5,Q6,Q8- Q12) were very discriminating and regarded as very good items with the indices of 0.41- 0.54. Two (2) items (Q4 and Q7) were poor with the indices of -0.09- -0.05

Table 2b: Summary of item discrimination for Mathematics Easy test items of 2019-2022 Examination Years

Year	Very Good	Good	Moderate	Marginal	Poor
2019	8 items	2items	1 item	-	1 item
Percent	67%	17%	8%	-	8%
2020	4 items	4 items	2 items	1 item	1 item

Percent	33%	33%	17%	8%	8%
2021	5 items	4 items	1 item	1 item	1 item
Percent	42%	33%	8%	8%	8%
2022	10 items	-	-	-	2 items
Percent	83%	-	-	-	17%

Table 2b shows the percentage of item discrimination index of NECO Mathematics easy examinations in 2019 to 2022. In 2019, 67% of the items had very good discriminating index 17% had discriminating index 8% had moderately discriminating index and 8% had poor discrimination index. In 2020, 33% of the items had very good discriminating index, 33% had good discriminating index, 17% had moderately discriminating index, 8% were not discriminating index and 8% had poor discrimination index.

In 2021, 42% of the items had very good discriminating index, 33% had good discriminating index, 8% had moderately discriminating index, 8% were not discriminating and 8% had poor discrimination index. In 2022, 83% of the items had very discriminating index and 17% had poor discrimination index.

Research Question Three

How do NECO Mathematics Essay test items drifted in the difficulty parameter from 2019-2022?

Research question 3 is answered using the mean differences in the difficulty parameters of NECO Mathematics easy questions of 2019-2022 presented on table 3 below:

Table 3: Analysis of Mean Differences in the Difficulty Parameter Estimates of NECO Mathematics Essay Questions of 2019-2022

Year	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference
2019	0.32	1.31	-0.12
2020	0.44	1.09	
2019	0.32	1.31	-0.22
2021	0.54	1.12	
2019	0.32	1.31	-0.54
2022	0.86	1.12	
2020	0.44	1.09	-0.10
2021	0.54	1.12	
2020	0.44	1.09	-0.42
2022	0.86	1.12	
2021	0.54	1.12	-0.32
2022	0.86		

The result of the analysis shows the mean differences in the difficulty indices of 2019-2020, 2019-2021, 2019-2022, 2020-2021, 2020-2022, 2021- 2022 were estimated to be, -0.12, -

0.22, -0.54, -0.10, -0.42 and -0.32. This indicates that the difficulty parameter drifted negatively within the study period of 2019-2022. This also means that the drift experienced within the period of examinations was a low drift.

Research Question Four

How do NECO Mathematics Essay test items drifted in the discrimination parameter from 2019-2022?

Research Question 4 is answered using Table 5 which shows the mean discrimination index of Mathematics essay questions of 2019-2022 examination years.

Table 4: Analysis of Mean Differences in discrimination Parameter of Mathematics essay NECO Questions of 2019-2022

Year	Mean	St. Deviation	Mean Difference
2019	0.37	0.23	0.05
2020	0.32	0.20	
2019	0.37	0.23	0.01
2021	0.36	0.23	
2019	0.37	0.23	-0.02
2022	0.39	0.21	
2020	0.32	0.20	-0.04
2021	0.36	0.23	
2020	0.32	0.20	-0.07
2022	0.39	0.21	
2021	0.36	0.23	-0.03
2022	0.39	0.21	

From table 4, the differences in the mean discrimination indices of Mathematics essay NECO questions of 2019-2020, 2019-2021, 2019-2022, 2020-2021, 2020-2022 and 2021-2022 was 0.05, 0.01, -0.02, -0.04, 0.07, and -0.03. This shows that 2019-2020 and 2019- 2021 had a medium drift in discrimination while 2019-2022, 2020-2021, 2020-2022 and 2021-2022 had a negative (low) drift discrimination.

Research Hypothesis One

The drift in the mean difficulty index of NECO Mathematics Essay test items of 2019-2022 do not significantly differ.

Hypothesis one was tested using One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on Table 5.

Table 5: Analysis of ANOVA Result of Drift in Difficulty index of Mathematics Essay NECO Questions of 2019-2022 examination years

Source variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Between Groups	4.862	3	1.62	0.403	.620	H ₀ : NS, NR
Within Groups	1623.14	404	4.02			
Total	1628.00	407				

F= 0.403, df= 3, p= 0.62; p> 0.05; NS = Not Significant; NR = H₀ is Not Rejected

Table 5 shows that F= 0.403 at between degree of freedom (df) of 3 and p significant value =0.62 and p set value =0.05. Since p> 0.05, this implies that the test hypothesis is not significant. Hence, the test hypothesis of no difference which states that the drift in the mean difficulty index of NECO Mathematics Essay test items of 2019-2022 do not significantly differ is not rejected.

Research Hypothesis Two

The drift in the mean discrimination index of NECO Mathematics Essay test items of 2019-2022 do not significantly differ.

Hypothesis two was tested using One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on table 6.

Table 6: ANOVA Result of Drift in the Discrimination index of Mathematics Essay NECO Questions of 2019-2022 examination years

Source variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Between Groups	3.862	3	1.29	0.32	.560	H ₀ : NS, NR
Within Groups	1628.138	404	4.030			
Total	1632.000	407				

F= 0.32, df= 3, p= 0.560; p> 0.05; NS = Not Significant; NR = Not Rejected

Table 6 shows that F= 0.32 at between degree of freedom (df) of 3 and p significant value =0.56 and p set value =0.05. Since p> 0.05, this implies that the test hypothesis is not significant. Hence, the test hypothesis of no difference which states that the drift in the mean discrimination index of NECO Mathematics Essay test items of 2019-2022 do not significantly differ is not rejected.

Discussion

The results of the analysis of data on research questions and null hypotheses were discussed based on the findings of the study on Assessing Item Parameter Drift of 2019-2022 National Examination Council Mathematics Essay Questions in Benue State, Nigeria.

Table 1(a and b) shows that 33% of the items were high, 42% of the items were medium and 25% of the items were low in 2019. The difficulty parameter values for the examination year ranged from -1.73 to 1.92. Three of the items had a negative difficulty index which indicates that they are very easy. The difficulty parameter of 2020 revealed that 33% of the items were high, 42% of the items were medium and 25% were low. The range of the difficulty index was from -1.03-1.70. Four items had a negative difficulty index which indicates that they are very easy and need to be reviewed.

The difficulty parameter of 2021 showed that 42% of the items were high, 42% of the items were medium and 17% percent of the items were low. The range of the difficulty index was from -1.10- 1.88. Three items had a negative index which indicates that the items were too easy and need to be reviewed.

The difficulty parameter of 2022 shows that 50% of the items were high, 33% of the items were medium while 17% of the items were low. The range of the difficulty index was from -1.56-1.93. Two of the items had a negative index which calls for the items to be reviewed. These findings are in line with Orherauta, Omoroguiwa and Osunde (2017) which shows items with negative index could lead to low (negative) drift indicating that the items are too easy and should be reviewed. This findings is at variance with that of Iornienge (2021) who found out that National examination items were of acceptable difficulty range. The findings also concurs with that of Awopeju and Afolabi (2010) who observed a positive drift in SSCE Mathematics NECO examination using the two parameter model.

Table 2b shows that in 2019, 92% of the items had acceptable item discrimination power. The range of the discrimination was from -0.18-0.51. 67% of the items had very good discriminating, 17% had good discriminating, 8% had moderately discriminating and 8% had poor discrimination.

In 2020, 83% of the items had acceptable item discrimination power. The range was from -0.17-0.48. 33% of the items had very good discriminating, 33% had good discriminating, 17% had moderately discriminating, 8% were not discriminating and 8% had poor discrimination

In 2021, 83% of the items had acceptable item discrimination power. The range was from -0.22- 0.553. 50% of the items had very good discriminating, 25% had good discriminating, 8% had moderately discriminating, 8% were not discriminating and 8% had poor discrimination.

In 2022, 83% of the items had acceptable item discrimination power. The range was from -0.09-0.55. 75% of the items had very good discriminating, 8% were not discriminating and 17% had poor discrimination.

Considering the discrimination parameter of the NECO Mathematics essay test items of 2019- 2022, 17 items altogether had negative discrimination. These items need to be reviewed to improve test quality. This is in agreement with Okoh (2020) that such items need to be worked upon to be used in further test to improve test quality. The discrimination power of the NECO Mathematics essay test items of 2019- 2022 shows that the items are generally good since they had more than 50% discrimination.

Table 3 shows that Mathematics Easy NECO questions of 2019 had a mean difficulty index of 0.32, that of 2020 was 0.44, 2021 was 0.54 and 2022 had a mean difficulty index of 0.86. The mean differences in the difficulty index of 2019-2020, 2019-2021, 2019-2022, 2020-2021, 2020-2022, 2021- 2022 was estimated to be, -0.12, -0.22, -0.54, -0.10, -0.42 and -0.32. This indicates that the difficulty parameter drifted negatively within the study period. This also means that the drift experienced within the period of the examination years was a negative (low) drift. This result agrees with that of Kyang, Han and Guo (2018) who found that items subjected to IPD exhibit a negative (low) drift and the items were too easy to the examinees. The findings also concurs with that of Kyan, Han and Guo (2018) who discovered a negative (low) drift in items subjected to IPD.

Table 4 shows that the mean discrimination of Mathematics essay NECO questions of 2019-2020, 2019-2021, 2019-2022, 2020-2021, 2020-2022 and 2021- 2022 was 0.05, 0.03, -0.02, -0.02, -0.07, and -0.05. This shows that 2019-2020 and 2019- 2021 had a medium drift in discrimination while 2019-2022, 2020-2021, 2020-2022 and 2021- 2022 had a negative (low) drift discrimination. This findings is in agreement with Orherauta, Omoroguiwa and Osunde (2017) who discovered that SSCE examination had some items with medium drift and others with a negative drift between 2012-2014.

Table 5 shows that differences in reliabilities between the years. For values computed using the coefficient-alpha method, the differences in the test reliabilities are 0.0269 between 2019 and 2020, 0.0191 between 2019 and 2021, and 0.0071 between 2019 and 2022. While between 2020 and 2021 was 0.046, between 2020 and 2022 was 0.034, and lastly between 2021 and 2022 was 0.012. This shows that the drift based on reliability was medium.

Table 6 revealed that the tested hypothesis is not significant. Hence, the test hypothesis of no difference which states that the drift in the mean difficulty index of NECO Mathematics Essay test items of 2019-2022 do not significantly differ is not rejected. This findings is in agreement with Krause (2016) who discovered that the level of drift in Mathematics examination was significant.

Table 7 revealed that the tested hypothesis is not significant. Hence, the test hypothesis of no difference which states that the drift in the mean discrimination index of NECO Mathematics Essay test items of 2019-2022 do not significantly differ is not rejected. This findings is at variance with that of Usal, Merve and Abdullah (2022); Amery, Zhen, Bruno and Zambo (2017) who discovered that the drift in national examination is significantly high.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the findings, the researcher concludes that the item parameters of NECO Mathematics essay test items have items with negative difficulty and discrimination parameters and exhibited no significant drift. These items need to be reviewed to ensure that when used in future examinations the test quality would be improved.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. The items that had negative parameter values should be reviewed to improve the quality of the examination in future usage.
- ii. A proper data documentation of essay item scores should be kept by NECO examination board to ensure the usage of the scores for research purposes. This will help improve the quality of the items for better pass and fail decisions.

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